

The impact of AI-generated recommendations on human decision-making in rule-based everyday scenarios: A user study with secondary school students

Krystian Czajka

WSB Merito University, Poland (lecturer)

Abstract

Background. AI-generated recommendations are increasingly embedded in the everyday digital environments used by adolescents, including educational platforms. Yet how young users weigh such recommendations against their own judgement in rule-based decisions - and how vulnerable they are when the AI is wrong - remains underexplored. **Objective.** We investigated whether AI-generated recommendations improve, degrade, or simply shift secondary school students' decisions on simple, rule-based scenarios drawn from a familiar context (school regulations), and whether students follow the AI even when it is demonstrably wrong. **Methods.** A between-subjects, individually randomised user study was conducted with 264 secondary school students (ages 16–18) at a single school complex (Zespół Szkół im. Narodów Zjednoczonej Europy in Polkowice, Lower Silesia, Poland). Participants completed an online questionnaire comprising 10 short rule-based scenarios with four answer options each. The treatment group (n = 140) received, alongside each scenario, an "AI recommendation" pointing to one option; 7 of the 10 recommendations were correct and 3 were intentionally incorrect. The control group (n = 124) received the same scenarios without any recommendation. Both groups were given a brief generic warning that AI systems can make mistakes and should not replace independent thinking. Differences between groups were analysed using Pearson's chi-square tests with Cramér's V as effect size, both per task and pooled. **Results.** Overall accuracy did not differ between groups (43.4% vs 42.5%, $\chi^2(1) = 0.17$, $p = .68$). However, the pattern depended strongly on whether the AI was correct. On the seven tasks where the AI was correct, the treatment group answered correctly slightly more often than the control group (44.2% vs 40.1%, $\chi^2(1) = 3.01$, $p = .083$); the effect was not uniform across items, and on Task 1 the control group was in fact more accurate. On the three tasks where the AI was wrong, the treatment group was less accurate (41.4% vs 48.1%, $\chi^2(1) = 3.31$, $p = .069$) and chose the AI-recommended (incorrect) option significantly more often than the control group chose the same option unaided (38.8% vs 27.7%, $\chi^2(1) = 10.45$, $p = .001$). The most pronounced single-task effect occurred on Task 5, where exposure to a misleading AI recommendation nearly doubled the rate at which students selected the wrong, recommended option (47.9% vs 24.2%, $\chi^2(3) = 17.01$, $p < .001$, Cramér's V = 0.254). **Conclusions.** AI recommendations exerted a measurable, asymmetric influence on adolescent decision-making in this sample: they helped modestly when correct and harmed substantially when wrong, with the harmful effect more reliably detectable than the helpful one. A generic warning that "AI can make mistakes" was insufficient to prevent over-reliance. The findings argue for explicit, scenario-grounded AI literacy in secondary education that goes beyond abstract caveats. **Keywords:** *AI-generated recommendations; automation bias; over-reliance; secondary education; AI literacy; human–AI decision-making.*

1. Introduction

Generative AI systems are now part of the everyday digital environment in which adolescents study, communicate, and make small decisions. Tools such as conversational assistants, recommender systems, and search-engine summaries routinely surface a single answer alongside the underlying material, framing it as authoritative. For school-age users, who often lack both the procedural experience and the metacognitive maturity to systematically question machine-generated outputs, this framing raises a practical question: when a familiar problem already has a clear, knowable answer, what happens to a young person's decision when an AI confidently points elsewhere?

The phenomenon at stake is not new. The human factors literature has documented "automation bias" - the tendency to defer to automated cues even when contradicting evidence is available - across aviation, clinical decision support, and intelligence analysis (Parasuraman & Riley, 1997; Skitka, Mosier, & Burdick, 1999; Goddard, Roudsari, & Wyatt, 2012). More recent work on AI-assisted decision-making has shown that adults take up algorithmic advice asymmetrically: helpful advice modestly improves accuracy, while flawed advice often substantially degrades it (Bansal et al., 2021; Buçinca, Malaya, & Gajos, 2021). Studies on "algorithm aversion" and "algorithm appreciation" further suggest that the magnitude of reliance is sensitive to framing, perceived competence of the system, and the user's domain expertise (Dietvorst, Simmons, & Massey, 2015; Logg, Minson, & Moore, 2019).

Adolescent users, however, are systematically under-represented in this literature. The bulk of empirical work on AI advice-taking has used university students, crowdworkers, or domain professionals. This is a non-trivial gap. Secondary school students are exposed to generative AI in school and private contexts, often without explicit instruction on its limits; they are also developmentally distinct from adult samples in terms of cognitive control, risk evaluation, and conformity to perceived authority (Steinberg, 2008). If, as Long and Magerko (2020) and Ng et al. (2021) argue, AI literacy is becoming a core competency for the next generation, we need direct evidence on how this group actually treats AI recommendations in tasks where the ground truth is known and the AI can be wrong.

The present study addresses this gap in a deliberately simple setting. We presented secondary school students (ages 16–18) with ten short, rule-based scenarios drawn from the everyday school environment - each in the form: *rule* → *situation* → *question* → *four answer options*. The rules were unambiguous and the scenarios were chosen to have a single defensible answer under each rule. Participants were randomly assigned to either receive an "AI recommendation" alongside each item or to answer unaided. Crucially, three of the ten recommendations were intentionally incorrect. This design lets us distinguish two competing accounts of AI's effect on adolescent decision-making: (i) a uniform-help account, in which the AI raises overall accuracy through anchoring on a confident, plausible answer; and (ii) an asymmetric-influence account, in which the AI helps when correct but harms when wrong, with the harm being non-trivial even after a general warning.

We pre-committed to three threads we wished to evaluate against the data: whether students over-rely on AI when its advice is wrong (automation bias); whether the help-versus-harm balance is symmetric or asymmetric, which has direct implications for AI literacy curricula; and what these effects mean for how AI competencies should be taught in secondary school. The findings, as we report below, fall most clearly in the second category - and we accordingly frame the discussion around the balanced view, while connecting it to the literatures on automation bias and AI literacy.

1.1. Research questions

We formulated three research questions:

- RQ1. Do AI-generated recommendations change the overall accuracy of secondary school students' decisions on simple, rule-based scenarios, compared to making the same decisions unaided?
- RQ2. Is the effect of AI recommendations symmetric with respect to the AI's correctness - that is, does the help received when the AI is right roughly equal the harm caused when the AI is wrong?
- RQ3. When the AI recommendation is demonstrably wrong, do students follow it more often than peers who answer without any AI recommendation arrive at the same wrong answer on their own?

2. Related Work

2.1. Automation bias and algorithmic advice-taking

Automation bias was originally characterised by Mosier and Skitka (1996) as the use of automated cues "as a heuristic replacement for vigilant information seeking and processing" - that is, as a shortcut that displaces, rather than supplements, the user's own evaluation of the situation (see also Parasuraman & Manzey, 2010). The literature typically distinguishes two failure modes: omission errors, where the user fails to act because the system did not flag a situation, and commission errors, where the user adopts an automation-suggested action that the available evidence does not support. The commission pattern is the one most directly relevant to our setting, because each of our scenarios contains a short, explicit rule that, on careful reading, is at odds with the incorrect recommendation.

Recent work on human–AI decision-making has refined this picture. Bansal et al. (2021) showed that joint accuracy in human–AI teams does not reliably exceed the accuracy of the better single party, and that supplying users with explanations of the AI's answer can in some cases push them further towards the AI's suggestion rather than towards independent verification - including when that suggestion is incorrect. Buçinca, Malaya, and Gajos (2021) demonstrated that "cognitive forcing functions" - design interventions that interrupt the user's flow and require an active reasoning step before the AI's answer is revealed - measurably reduce over-reliance. Vasconcelos et al. (2023) describe over-reliance as the outcome of a strategic trade-off in which the user weighs the effort of independently verifying the task against the perceived utility of simply accepting the AI's output. In our scenarios that verification cost is deliberately kept low - the rule is short, the situation is short, and a single re-reading is sufficient - and yet, as our results show, over-reliance still emerges.

2.2. Algorithm appreciation, aversion, and trust calibration

A complementary line of work has asked when humans actually prefer algorithmic advice. Logg, Minson, and Moore (2019) found that non-expert participants weighted algorithmic advice more heavily than equivalent human advice - a tendency they termed "algorithm appreciation." Dietvorst, Simmons, and Massey (2015) found the opposite pattern, "algorithm aversion," when users had seen an algorithm err. These two findings are not contradictory: they describe different points on a trust-calibration curve. Adolescent users in our study, who interact daily with consumer-facing AI products

that rarely surface errors saliently, are plausibly closer to the appreciation regime than the aversion regime at the time of testing.

2.3. AI literacy in secondary education

AI literacy has been proposed as a transversal competency for secondary education, defined by Long and Magerko (2020) as the set of skills that lets individuals "critically evaluate AI technologies; communicate and collaborate effectively with AI; and use AI as a tool online, at home, and in the workplace" (p. 2); subsequent reviews have extended and refined this framing (Ng, Leung, Chu, & Qiao, 2021). Empirical work in this space has, however, focused predominantly on conceptual understanding - what an AI system is, how it learns, what a model is - rather than on the behavioural skill of calibrated use: deciding when, and how much, to trust a particular output. Our study contributes to the latter strand by providing a low-stakes, observable behavioural measure of how secondary school students actually respond to plausible-looking AI advice on questions with knowable answers, and by quantifying the cost of a generic "AI can make mistakes" warning of the kind that is typically issued in classroom settings.

3. Methods

3.1. Design

The study used a between-subjects design with two conditions: AI-recommendation (treatment) versus no-recommendation (control). Each participant completed the same set of ten rule-based scenarios; only the presence or absence of an AI recommendation varied across conditions. Participants were individually randomised to a condition at the start of the questionnaire.

3.2. Setting and participants

Participants were 264 secondary school students aged 16–18 from a single school complex in Poland: Zespół Szkół im. Narodów Zjednoczonej Europy in Polkowice (Lower Silesia), which comprises a general secondary school (liceum ogólnokształcące) and a technical secondary school (technikum). The study was conducted as part of authorised in-class workshops on AI and decision-making led by the author. The school administration consented to the study; all student responses were anonymous and no identifying information was collected. Because the study involved only anonymous responses to non-sensitive school-related scenarios as part of routine educational activity, formal review by an external bioethics committee was not required under the applicable Polish institutional practice for non-invasive educational research; the protocol nevertheless followed the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki, including voluntary participation and the right to withdraw at any point. Students were informed verbally about the purpose of the workshop and that their anonymous responses would be used for research; the school acted as gatekeeper consistent with local practice for non-invasive classroom-based studies.

Of the 264 participants, 140 were randomly assigned to the AI-recommendation condition and 124 to the control condition. One scenario (Task 10) in the AI condition received 141 responses due to a single delayed submission. Pre-existing class composition (general vs technical track) was not used as a stratification variable. The sample was a convenience sample comprising all students from the participating school complex who attended the workshop sessions; no a priori power analysis was conducted. With $n = 264$ and a two-proportion comparison, the achieved sample provides

approximately 80% power to detect a difference of 10 percentage points at $\alpha = .05$ (two-sided), which is in the range of effects reported in adjacent human–AI decision-making studies (e.g., Bućinca et al., 2021). The study was not pre-registered; the three threads listed in Section 1 were planned analyses, but the per-task tests reported in Section 4 should be treated as exploratory.

3.3. Materials

Ten short scenarios were constructed by the author in consultation with teaching staff at the participating school. Each scenario followed an identical four-part structure:

- Rule (Zasada): one or two sentences stating a school regulation in unambiguous form (e.g., "Only a simple calculator is permitted during a test. Mobile phones are not a permitted tool, regardless of mode of operation.").
- Situation (Sytuacja): one or two sentences describing a concrete situation in which the rule is to be applied.
- Question (Pytanie): a single closed question of the form "What follows from the rule?" or "How should this situation be evaluated?".
- Four answer options (A–D), exactly one of which was the intended correct answer under the rule.

The scenarios covered familiar school topics: permitted tools during tests, deadlines and technical failures, collaboration and authorship, conflicts between written regulations and oral instructions, materials brought into exams, retake eligibility, in-class phone use, eligibility of external help in competitions, the scope of medical excuses, and the scope of short quizzes (kartkówki). All items were presented in Polish. Full English translations are provided in Appendix A.

For the AI-recommendation condition, each scenario was accompanied by a short "AI recommendation" (Rekomendacja AI) of the form: "Answer X, because [one-sentence rationale]." Seven of the ten recommendations pointed to the intended correct option (Tasks 1, 3, 4, 6, 7, 8, 10). Three were intentionally incorrect (Tasks 2, 5, 9): the recommendation pointed to a plausible-looking but rule-inconsistent option, accompanied by a superficially reasonable justification. The wrong recommendations were placed in non-adjacent positions in the questionnaire and did not visually differ from the correct ones. The control condition received the identical scenarios with the "Rekomendacja AI" block omitted; everything else was held constant.

3.4. Procedure

The study was administered as an online questionnaire (Google Forms) during a single workshop session under the supervision of the author. Participants completed the questionnaire individually on their own devices while seated in a shared classroom; they were instructed not to confer. Before starting, all participants were given a brief generic warning, in Polish, conveying that AI systems can make mistakes and that respondents should rely on their own judgement; the warning was presented orally and on the first screen of the questionnaire (English rendering: "Artificial-intelligence systems can be wrong. Read each rule and situation carefully, and choose the answer that follows from the rule, even if the AI suggests otherwise."). No worked examples, scenario-specific cautions, or accuracy figures for the AI were provided. Participants in the treatment condition were not told how many of the AI recommendations were correct or incorrect. Completion took approximately 10–15 minutes.

3.5. Measures

For each task we computed two primary outcomes per group: (i) the proportion of participants choosing the rule-consistent (correct) option, and (ii) the proportion of participants choosing the AI-recommended option. On the seven tasks where the AI was correct these two proportions coincide; on the three tasks where the AI was wrong they diverge and become diagnostic of over-reliance.

We additionally computed three pooled measures across all participants and all tasks: overall accuracy, accuracy on AI-correct tasks, and accuracy on AI-wrong tasks. To assess over-reliance specifically, we computed the rate at which participants in the treatment group selected the AI-recommended option on the three AI-wrong tasks, and compared it with the rate at which control participants selected that same option unaided.

3.6. Statistical analysis

Per-task differences in the full A/B/C/D response distribution were tested using Pearson's chi-square test of independence with Cramér's V as the effect size; columns that received zero responses in both groups were dropped from the test to preserve degrees of freedom. Pooled outcomes were tested using 2×2 chi-square tests on correct-vs-incorrect counts. Reported p -values are two-sided and uncorrected for multiplicity; we treat per-task tests as exploratory and place primary interpretive weight on the pre-specified pooled comparisons. All analyses were performed in Python 3 (SciPy 1.x).

4. Results

4.1. Overall accuracy

Pooled across all ten tasks and all participants, accuracy was nearly identical between conditions: 43.4% (608 of 1,401 responses) in the AI-recommendation group versus 42.5% (527 of 1,239 responses) in the control group, $\chi^2(1) = 0.17$, $p = .68$. Considered in aggregate, exposure to AI recommendations did not appear to change how often students arrived at the rule-consistent answer.

This aggregate null result, however, conceals two opposing effects that emerge once the tasks are split by AI correctness - and the split is also not perfectly uniform within each subset, as we describe next.

4.2. Effect of AI on tasks where the AI was correct

On the seven tasks where the AI recommendation pointed to the rule-consistent option, the treatment group answered correctly more often than the control group in aggregate: 44.2% (434/981) versus 40.1% (348/867), $\chi^2(1) = 3.01$, $p = .083$. The direction is consistent with anchoring on a confident, correct cue, but the magnitude is modest and the pooled test does not reach conventional significance. The effect was also not uniform across items. The largest positive contribution came from Task 8 (work-authorship rule), where the treatment group exceeded the control group by 12.4 percentage points (47.1% vs 34.7%). Conversely, Task 1 (calculator-vs-phone rule) showed the opposite direction: only 34.3% of the AI group chose the correct option C, against 39.8% in the control group. On Task 1 the most popular answer in both groups was the rule-inconsistent option D ("the student may use the phone if the teacher consents"), chosen by 50.0% of the AI group and 37.4% of the control group - suggesting that on this item a strong pre-existing intuition pulled answers towards D regardless of the AI cue, and possibly in spite of it. We return to this asymmetry across items in the Discussion.

4.3. Effect of AI on tasks where the AI was wrong

On the three tasks where the AI recommendation was intentionally wrong, the pattern reversed. Accuracy was lower in the treatment group than in the control group: 41.4% (174/420) versus 48.1% (179/372), $\chi^2(1) = 3.31$, $p = .069$. As with the AI-correct subset, the pooled test for accuracy is at the edge of conventional significance, but the diagnostic measure - the rate at which participants chose the AI-recommended option - tells a sharper story (Section 4.4).

4.4. Over-reliance on incorrect AI recommendations

Across the three AI-wrong tasks, 38.8% of treatment-group responses (163/420) selected the option that the AI had recommended, compared to 27.7% (103/372) of control-group responses landing on the same option unaided. The difference is statistically robust: $\chi^2(1) = 10.45$, $p = .001$, with a 95% confidence interval on the difference in proportions of [4.6, 17.6] percentage points. In other words, the presence of a confident, plausible-looking AI recommendation increased the probability of selecting that specific wrong option by roughly 11 percentage points - a relative increase of about 40% over the baseline rate at which students arrive at the same wrong answer on their own.

The most dramatic single-task instance was Task 5, which concerned an unambiguous rule prohibiting any in-test additions to a "formula card." The AI recommended option D ("Permitted, because the final state of the card complies with the rule"). In the treatment group, 47.9% chose D; in the control group, only 24.2% did ($\chi^2(3) = 17.01$, $p < .001$, Cramér's $V = 0.254$ - by Cohen's conventional benchmarks, a small-to-medium effect for nominal data). Correspondingly, accuracy on Task 5 was nearly halved in the treatment group (25.7% vs 40.3%).

Task 9 (medical-excuse scope) shows a related but more subtle pattern. Here the AI recommended option A ("not excused, because the student appeared at school"), while the rule-consistent answer was option B ("excused, because the excuse covers the whole day"). The share choosing the AI-recommended A was 17.9% in the treatment group versus 7.3% in the control group - more than a two-fold increase in absolute terms, although on a small base. The corresponding cost in accuracy was a drop from 63.7% (control) to 53.6% (treatment) on the correct option B. The wrong AI cue did not produce a wholesale migration to A, but it visibly shifted a fraction of students away from the correct answer.

Task 2 stands out as a partial exception. The AI recommended option B (a plausible "good-faith" interpretation in which the student's e-mail outside the official channel still counts as submitted on time). The correct answer under the rule is A (no, it was not submitted via the required channel), but the share choosing B was almost identical in both groups (50.7% vs 51.6%). The most defensible reading is that this scenario is intuitively ambiguous: many students arrived at the "good-faith" reading on their own, leaving little room for the AI cue to add further influence. The pattern across the three AI-wrong tasks is therefore not uniform - but in none of them does the AI cue protect against, or even leave unchanged, the rate of the wrong answer it itself recommends.

Table 1. Per-task results.

Task	Correct	AI rec.	% correct (AI / Ctrl)	% chose AI-rec. (AI / Ctrl)	χ^2	p	V
1	C	C ✓	34.3 / 39.8	34.3 / 39.8	4.68	.197	0.133
2	A	B ✗	45.0 / 40.3	50.7 / 51.6	1.90	.388	0.085
3	C	C ✓	42.1 / 37.1	42.1 / 37.1	2.44	.487	0.096
4	B	B ✓	37.9 / 37.1	37.9 / 37.1	3.23	.358	0.111
5	A	D ✗	25.7 / 40.3	47.9 / 24.2	17.01	< .001	0.254
6	C	C ✓	55.7 / 48.4	55.7 / 48.4	5.88	.117	0.149
7	C	C ✓	26.4 / 24.2	26.4 / 24.2	3.64	.303	0.117
8	A	A ✓	47.1 / 34.7	47.1 / 34.7	4.34	.227	0.128
9	B	A ✗	53.6 / 63.7	17.9 / 7.3	7.71	.052	0.171
10	C	C ✓	66.0 / 59.7	66.0 / 59.7	3.26	.353	0.111

Notes. $n = 140$ (AI) and 124 (Control) for all tasks except Task 10 ($n = 141$ AI). Per-task χ^2 tested the full A/B/C/D distribution between groups; columns with zero responses in both groups were dropped, so per-task degrees of freedom are $df = 2$ or $df = 3$ depending on the item. Cramér's V is reported as effect size. ✓ = AI recommendation matched the correct answer; ✗ = AI recommendation was intentionally incorrect.

Table 2. Pooled results.

Comparison	AI group	Control	$\chi^2(1)$	p
Overall accuracy (all 10 tasks)	608/1401 = 43.4%	527/1239 = 42.5%	0.17	.683
Accuracy when AI was correct (7 tasks)	434/981 = 44.2%	348/867 = 40.1%	3.01	.083
Accuracy when AI was wrong (3 tasks)	174/420 = 41.4%	179/372 = 48.1%	3.31	.069
Rate of choosing AI-rec. answer on AI-wrong tasks	163/420 = 38.8%	103/372 = 27.7%	10.45	.001

Notes. The first three rows compare accuracy. The last row, the central over-reliance test, compares the rate at which the AI-recommended (and incorrect) option was chosen in each group on the same three items.

4.5. Summary of findings against the research questions

Returning to the pre-specified research questions: with respect to RQ1, AI recommendations did not change overall accuracy in this sample. With respect to RQ2, the effect of AI was clearly asymmetric: a modest, non-significant aggregate benefit when the AI was right (about +4 percentage points pooled, with at least one item - Task 1 - running in the opposite direction) was paired with a non-trivial cost when it was wrong, visible most clearly in the diagnostic over-reliance measure rather than in raw

accuracy. With respect to RQ3, students in the treatment group followed the AI's wrong recommendations substantially and significantly more often than control-group peers arrived at the same wrong answer unaided.

5. Discussion

Three things stand out in our results. First, AI recommendations were not a uniformly good thing or a uniformly bad thing for adolescent decision-makers in this sample - they shifted behaviour in the direction the AI pointed, regardless of whether that direction was correct, with the size of the shift depending on the item. Second, the harmful effect was easier to detect than the helpful effect: in the same sample, the pooled over-reliance test reached $p = .001$, while the benefit-when-correct test only reached $p = .083$. Third, the harmful effect persisted despite an explicit, general warning that AI can make mistakes.

5.1. AI as an asymmetric influence, not a uniform aid

Our central, balanced framing - AI helps when correct and harms when wrong - is consistent with the broader human-AI decision-making literature in adult and professional samples (Bansal et al., 2021; Buçinca et al., 2021). What our study adds is direct evidence of this pattern in 16–18-year-old secondary-school users on extremely simple, knowable scenarios. The simplicity of the materials matters: students who chose the AI-recommended wrong answer were not failing to grasp the rule. The rule fit in two lines and the scenario in two more. They were, in many cases, failing to override a confident-looking recommendation in a context where overriding it should have been close to costless.

It is also worth noting that the asymmetry across items is not the same as a symmetric error around the AI recommendation. Task 1 in particular, where the AI was correct but the AI group ended up less accurate than the control group, suggests that pre-existing intuition can dominate the AI cue when the intuition is sufficiently strong. The cleanest summary is therefore neither "AI helps" nor "AI harms" but rather: in this sample, the AI recommendation shifts a fraction of responses towards the option it endorses, where that fraction is sometimes outweighed by competing intuitive pulls, and where the net effect on accuracy is determined by whether the AI happens to agree with the rule or not.

The over-reliance signal in our data is statistically stronger than the benefit signal, but this comparison alone should not be read as a claim that AI on balance hurts these students. The number of AI-correct items (seven) is larger than the number of AI-wrong items (three), and the per-item shifts on most items run in the expected direction. The more cautious and policy-relevant reading is that the asymmetry between gain and loss is not in the user's favour: each correct AI cue moves a fraction of students towards the right answer, while each incorrect AI cue moves a comparable fraction of students towards a specific wrong answer that they would, on their own, have been less likely to select.

5.2. Automation bias under a generic warning

All participants - both treatment and control - were told, before starting, that AI can make mistakes and should not replace their own judgement (the exact wording is reported in Section 3.4). This is roughly the level of caution that a thoughtful teacher gives during a normal lesson involving AI tools. It was not sufficient: in the treatment condition, the 11-percentage-point increase in choosing the AI-recommended wrong option, against this warning, is a quantitative reminder that generic disclaimers do not produce calibrated trust. The mechanism is consistent with the cost-benefit account of

Vasconcelos et al. (2023): when the cognitive cost of verifying a confident-looking recommendation is itself non-trivial (re-reading the rule, considering all four options, resisting the social cue of an "AI recommendation"), and the perceived reliability of the system is high, deferring is the locally efficient strategy - even when, as here, verification is in fact very cheap.

5.3. Implications for AI literacy in secondary education

Our findings argue against treating AI literacy as a purely conceptual topic, taught alongside abstract definitions of "machine learning" or "large language model." Conceptual knowledge is necessary but not, on this evidence, sufficient to immunise students against over-reliance on a single confident recommendation. We see at least three concrete implications for curriculum design:

- **Calibrated-use exercises.** Students should encounter, in classroom exercises, AI outputs that are intentionally wrong on questions they themselves can verify. The point is not to teach distrust but to give students felt experience of catching a confident-looking error, so that the act of verification becomes a habit rather than an effortful exception.
- **Explicit verification heuristics.** Generic warnings ("AI can make mistakes") should be replaced or supplemented with concrete procedures: re-read the rule before reading the recommendation; check whether the recommendation's rationale actually entails the recommended option; consider what each of the other options would imply.
- **Domain-specific framing.** AI recommendations in scenarios with clear rules (school regulations, legal rules, safety procedures) are a different cognitive object than recommendations in scenarios with uncertain ground truth (essay style, route choice, recipe suggestions). Curricula should distinguish these explicitly, because the appropriate level of independent verification differs.

The Task 2 result is instructive here. Where the underlying scenario already admits a strong "good-faith" intuition that competes with the literal rule, AI recommendations add relatively little new variance to the response distribution - the students are, in effect, already making the same judgement the AI is making. Calibrated-use training should therefore aim less at "doubting the AI" in the abstract and more at building the specific skill of returning to the rule when the AI and intuition coincide.

5.4. Limitations

Several limitations bear on the interpretation of these results. The study was conducted at a single school complex, which constrains generalisability beyond the local population. Although individual randomisation was used within sessions, participants were not blinded to their condition in the trivial sense that the AI-recommendation block was visible to them. We did not collect prior AI experience, attitudes towards AI, academic performance, or track (general vs technical) as covariates; including these in future work would help establish moderators of over-reliance. The "AI recommendations" themselves were author-generated mock outputs rather than the actual output of a deployed system; this gives experimental control over correctness but may under- or overestimate the rhetorical force of, for example, a chatbot answer with formatting, hedges, and citations. Finally, the rule-based, multiple-choice format is a deliberate simplification: real-world AI assistance more often involves open-ended outputs and noisier ground truths.

5.5. Future work

Three extensions would be especially informative. First, a within-subjects manipulation in which the same students see correct and incorrect AI recommendations across matched scenarios would let us estimate individual-level trust calibration, and identify students who reliably override the AI versus those who reliably defer. Second, an intervention study in which one randomised arm receives an explicit verification-heuristic training before the same task battery would test whether the over-reliance effect we observed is in fact remediable by short, classroom-feasible instruction. Third, replacing mock recommendations with live outputs of contemporary LLMs would let us examine whether more sophisticated AI behaviours - hedging, citing rules, asking clarifying questions - change the over-reliance pattern, and in which direction.

6. Conclusion

In a study of 264 secondary school students aged 16–18, AI-generated recommendations had no overall effect on accuracy in simple, rule-based school scenarios - but this null aggregate concealed an asymmetric pattern of help and harm that varied across items. When the AI recommendation was correct, students were modestly and inconsistently more likely to give the correct answer. When the AI recommendation was wrong, students chose the wrong answer the AI pointed to substantially and significantly more often than peers who answered the same items without an AI cue. A generic, pre-task warning that AI can make mistakes did not prevent this over-reliance. For schools introducing AI tools to adolescents, the practical implication is that conceptual AI literacy needs to be complemented by calibrated-use practice on tasks where the student can verify the AI for themselves - and where, occasionally, the AI is allowed to be visibly wrong, so that catching a confident-looking error becomes a learned habit rather than an exception.

Declarations

Ethics approval. The study was approved by the administration of the participating school and conducted in line with the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki. Participation was voluntary, responses were anonymous, and no personally identifying information was collected. Under the applicable Polish institutional practice for non-invasive educational research involving anonymous responses to non-sensitive school-related scenarios, review by an external bioethics committee was not required.

Consent to participate. Students were informed verbally about the purpose of the workshop and the research use of their anonymous responses; participation in the questionnaire was voluntary and could be discontinued at any point.

Funding. This research received no specific grant from any funding agency in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Competing interests. The author declares no competing interests.

Data and code availability. Aggregated per-task response distributions used to compute all reported statistics are available in Table 1 and the body of the Results section. Raw individual-level response data and analysis scripts are available from the author on reasonable request, subject to the constraints

of the school's consent arrangements; no individual-level data are shared publicly in order to protect participant anonymity at a single-school site.

Author contributions. The author is solely responsible for study conception, design, materials, data collection, analysis, and writing of the manuscript.

Use of AI tools. Generative AI tools were used to assist with English-language editing and with cross-checking statistical computations. All scientific decisions, interpretations, and the final wording are the author's own. AI tools were not used to generate the participant-facing materials (rules, scenarios, options, or "AI recommendations"), all of which were authored manually as described in Section 3.3.

References

- Bansal, G., Wu, T., Zhou, J., Fok, R., Nushi, B., Kamar, E., Ribeiro, M. T., & Weld, D. S. (2021). Does the whole exceed its parts? The effect of AI explanations on complementary team performance. In *Proceedings of the 2021 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (pp. 1–16). ACM.
- Buçınca, Z., Malaya, M. B., & Gajos, K. Z. (2021). To trust or to think: Cognitive forcing functions can reduce overreliance on AI in AI-assisted decision-making. *Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction*, 5(CSCW1), Article 188.
- Dietvorst, B. J., Simmons, J. P., & Massey, C. (2015). Algorithm aversion: People erroneously avoid algorithms after seeing them err. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General*, 144(1), 114–126.
- Goddard, K., Roudsari, A., & Wyatt, J. C. (2012). Automation bias: A systematic review of frequency, effect mediators, and mitigators. *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association*, 19(1), 121–127.
- Logg, J. M., Minson, J. A., & Moore, D. A. (2019). Algorithm appreciation: People prefer algorithmic to human judgment. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 151, 90–103.
- Long, D., & Magerko, B. (2020). What is AI literacy? Competencies and design considerations. In *Proceedings of the 2020 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (pp. 1–16). ACM.
- Mosier, K. L., & Skitka, L. J. (1996). Human decision makers and automated decision aids: Made for each other? In R. Parasuraman & M. Mouloua (Eds.), *Automation and human performance: Theory and applications* (pp. 201–220). Lawrence Erlbaum.
- Ng, D. T. K., Leung, J. K. L., Chu, S. K. W., & Qiao, M. S. (2021). Conceptualizing AI literacy: An exploratory review. *Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence*, 2, 100041.
- Parasuraman, R., & Manzey, D. H. (2010). Complacency and bias in human use of automation: An attentional integration. *Human Factors*, 52(3), 381–410.
- Parasuraman, R., & Riley, V. (1997). Humans and automation: Use, misuse, disuse, abuse. *Human Factors*, 39(2), 230–253.
- Skitka, L. J., Mosier, K. L., & Burdick, M. D. (1999). Does automation bias decision-making? *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies*, 51(5), 991–1006.
- Steinberg, L. (2008). A social neuroscience perspective on adolescent risk-taking. *Developmental Review*, 28(1), 78–106.

Vasconcelos, H., Jörke, M., Grunde-McLaughlin, M., Gerstenberg, T., Bernstein, M. S., & Krishna, R. (2023). Explanations can reduce overreliance on AI systems during decision-making. *Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction*, 7(CSCW1), Article 129.

Appendix A. Scenarios used in the study (English translation)

All scenarios were originally presented to participants in Polish. The English renderings below are working translations preserving the rule → situation → question → options structure used in the questionnaire. The correct option under the stated rule and the AI recommendation are indicated.

Task 1 - Simple calculator vs. phone

Rule. Only a simple calculator is permitted during a test. Mobile phones are not a permitted tool, regardless of mode of operation.

Situation. A student does not have a simple calculator but has a phone in airplane mode and wants to use a calculator app.

Question. What follows from the rule?

Options. A) May use the phone (calculator function is the same); B) May use the phone (no internet); C) May not use the phone (phone is not a permitted tool) - correct, AI ✓; D) May use the phone if the teacher consents.

Task 2 - Homework submission deadline

Rule. Homework must be submitted via the e-diary by 20:00.

Situation. A student sends the work to the teacher by e-mail at 19:55, because the e-diary is not working at that time.

Question. Per the rule, was the work submitted?

Options. A) Yes, because it was sent before 20:00 - correct; B) Yes, because the technical problem was not the student's fault - AI X; C) No, the work was not submitted via the e-diary; D) No, e-mail is not an official channel.

Task 3 - Joint discussion, identical answers

Rule. Students may discuss tasks together, but submitted answers must be independently formulated. Answers with identical structure and identical phrasing will be treated as non-independent.

Situation. Two students submit separate files containing identical justifications in the same order.

Question. How should this situation be evaluated?

Options. A) Rule met (each submitted own file); B) Rule met (collaboration was allowed); C) Rule not met (answers not independent) - correct, AI ✓; D) Cannot be judged without talking to the students.

Task 4 - Written rule vs. oral instruction

Rule. In a conflict between the school regulations and an oral decision of the teacher, the school regulations apply.

Situation. The school regulations forbid eating in the computer lab. The teacher leading the class tells students they may eat in the room that day.

Question. What follows from the rule?

Options. A) Apply the teacher's decision; B) Apply the school regulations - correct, AI ✓; C) The students should decide; D) Apply a compromise solution.

Task 5 - Formula card additions during the test

Rule. A formula card may contain only material prepared before the test. Nothing may be added during the test.

Situation. A student pencils a formula onto the card during the test, then erases it before handing in the work.

Question. How should this behaviour be evaluated?

Options. A) Not allowed (addition occurred during the test) - correct; B) Not allowed only if the teacher noticed; C) Allowed if the addition was not used; D) Allowed because the final state of the card complies with the rule - AI X.

Task 6 - Retake eligibility

Rule. A student is entitled to a retake of a test only in the case of a failing grade.

Situation. A student received a passing (but low) grade and asks for a retake.

Question. What follows from the rule?

Options. A) Has the right (the grade was low); B) Has the right if the teacher consents; C) Does not have the right (does not meet the rule's condition) - correct, AI ✓; D) Has the right if the point difference was small.

Task 7 - Phone for checking the time

Rule. On school premises, using mobile phones is forbidden during lessons.

Situation. A student checks the time on the phone during a lesson, using no other functions.

Question. How should this be evaluated?

Options. A) Allowed (no internet/app use); B) Allowed (very brief); C) Not allowed (use of the phone occurred) - correct, AI ✓; D) Allowed if phone was on silent.

Task 8 - Linguistic correction in competition work

Rule. Competition work must be done independently by the student.

Situation. A student writes the work alone but asks the teacher to correct language errors before submission.

Question. Does the work satisfy the independence requirement?

Options. A) Yes (substantive content was the student's) - correct, AI ✓; B) Yes (linguistic correction does not change content); C) No (another person intervened in the work); D) No (teacher should not help in competitions).

Task 9 - Scope of a medical excuse

Rule. A medical excuse covers the period indicated on the certificate.

Situation. A student holds an excuse for the whole day, but comes to school for only one lesson.

Question. How should the absences from the remaining hours be treated?

Options. A) Not excused (the student appeared at school) - AI X; B) Excused (the excuse covers the whole day) - correct; C) Not excused (student was partially present); D) Depends on the form tutor's decision.

Task 10 - Scope of a short quiz (kartkówka)

Rule. A short quiz (kartkówka) may cover material from the last three lessons.

Situation. A student was absent for one of the last three lessons and did not study that material.

Question. May the quiz include content from that lesson?

Options. A) No (the student did not attend); B) No, if the student has a medical excuse; C) Yes (the rule defines the scope of material, not attendance) - correct, AI ✓; D) Yes, only if the teacher gave prior notice.